

ISic0605

I.Sicily inscription 0605

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

D'Orville saw it 'in vestibulo domus episcopi'

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. L(ucius) [---]onn[ius]
2. LI(uci) fe(ilius) QOuir(ina) Nomen
3. tarnus nomine [suo]
4. et Clodi Thiori
5. ani collegae
6. ex aere DAN[]
7. RINENNI aedi
8. litatis suae re
9. liqqua [pe]cunia
10. de suoasdiectla
11. l(oco) d(ato) d(ecreto) d(ecurionum)

Apparatus

Text of I.Lipara

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491870

EDR 159440

EDCS 22100609

PHI 334865

Bibliography

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